

MOTIVATION AS A PART OF THE MANAGEMENT ROLE. WAYS TO MOTIVATE THE PERSONNEL

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Abstract: *This passage outlines the purpose and scope of employee motivation management inside the company. The management of employee motivation is one of the primary roles of management, from which particular focus is drawn. The article outlines the primary elements affecting the employees' drive to work and describes how managers can best support their subordinates' motivation. The primary forms of motivation that drive the employees of the organization are outlined. Additionally, F. Herzberg's two-factor theory of motivation is explained. in the outset of the development of staff motivational profiles.*

Key words: *supervisory functions, incentives, manager, non-monetary incentives, methods of inspiring employees to work, management, requirements.*

The essence of any activity is manifested in its functions. Functions imply the purpose of the activities of any organization or its general task. As well as the type of managerial actions and the scope of specific decision-making.

The main functions of management, defined by Henri Fayol as early as 1916, are planning, organizing, controlling, and coordinating. However, the efficiency of any economic and production process cannot be determined only by these basic functions. No less important factor than an effective organizational structure, agreed goals and clearly defined tasks is the quality of the staff's work. Which directly depends on the staff. Motivation is used to improve the quality of work of subordinates. Motivation as a function of management is directly related to the motivation of personnel to be effective in their work through the formation of motives. Motivation is a person's conscious choice of a particular type of behavior, so motivation as a management function should be directly aimed at increasing the labor activity of employees. Based on a clear understanding of the behavior of personnel, motivation as a management function helps to develop and improve ways to maximize the result of work. In the process of developing the most effective ways to achieve results, it is necessary to take into account the interrelated categories of employee behavior: needs, interests, motives and actions. To do this, managers use certain methods with the help of which managerial influence on personnel is carried out. Actions are based on the laws of management, as they suggest the use of various forms of influence on the personnel of the organization.

Methods of motivation in management can be of a material and non-material nature. Material methods consist of financial incentives for employees by changing the level of wages, giving bonuses or monetary rewards. Intangible methods include methods that allow the employee to participate in the organizational activities of the company, achieve success in the team, personal development and other intangible factors.

The main demotivators that directly affect the quality of work are: incompetence of the manager, undeserved criticism, overload or underwork, unclarity of job functions or functions of the company.

Many HR professionals use classical theories of motivation, but they may not be effective if they are not tailored to the needs of a particular organization and specific employees. The true motivations that drive one to do their best are difficult to determine, yet they are extremely complex. However, by mastering modern models of motivation, the manager will be able to significantly

expand his or her ability to attract an educated, experienced employee of today to perform tasks aimed at achieving the goals of the organization.

Modern Theories of Motivation. In planning and organizing work, the manager determines what exactly the organization should do, when, how, and by whom, in his opinion, should do it. If the choice of these decisions is made effectively, the manager is able to coordinate the efforts of many people and jointly realize the potential of the group of employees. In order to effectively move towards the goal, the manager must coordinate the work and motivate people to high-quality performance of the assigned tasks. Managers put their decisions into action by putting into practice the basic principles of motivation. Motivation (from Latin: *movere*) — inducement to action; a psychophysiological process that governs human behavior, determines its direction, organization, activity, and stability; the ability of a person to actively satisfy his needs.

A systematic study of motivation from a psychological point of view does not allow us to determine exactly what motivates a person to work. However, research on human behavior at work provides some general explanations of motivation and allows for the creation of pragmatic models of employee motivation in the workplace. Psychologists say that a person feels a need when he or she feels a physiological or psychological lack of something. Although a particular person may not have a need in the sense of consciously feeling it at a particular time, there are certain needs that each person can feel. Substantive Theories of Motivation represent attempts to classify these universal human needs into certain categories. There is still no universally accepted identification of certain needs. However, most psychologists agree that needs can in principle be classified as primary and secondary.

Primary needs are physiological in nature and usually innate. Examples include food, water, breathing, sleeping, and sexual needs. Secondary needs are psychological in nature. For example, the need for success, respect, affection, power, and the need to belong to someone or something. Primary needs are genetically determined, and secondary needs are usually recognized through experience. Because people have different experiences, people's secondary needs differ more than their primary needs.

Needs and motivational behavior. Needs cannot be directly observed or measured; they can only be assessed. The existence of needs can be judged by people's behavior and by assessing the employee's motivational profile. Psychologists, observing people, have determined that needs serve as a motive for action [3, 154]. When a need is felt by a person, it awakens in him a state of striving. An urge is a feeling of lacking in something that has a certain direction. It is a behavioral manifestation of a need and is focused on achieving a goal. Ends, in this sense, are something that is recognized as a means of satisfying a need. When a person achieves such a goal, his need is satisfied, partially satisfied, or unsatisfied. Since needs cause a person to want to satisfy them, managers must create situations that allow people to feel that they can satisfy their needs through certain behaviors and actions that lead to the achievement of the organization's goals.

There are a great variety of specific human needs, those goals that each person understands lead to the satisfaction of his needs, as well as the types of behavior in achieving these goals.

A leader must always keep in mind the element of chance, there is no one best way to motivate. What turns out to be effective in motivating some people turns out to be completely unimportant for others. In addition, organizations inherently complicate the practical implementation of individual-centered theories of motivation. The interdependence of work, the lack of information in the work results of individuals, the frequent changes in job responsibilities due to improvements in technology - all this exacerbates the complexity of motivation.

According to Herzberg's two-factor theory of motivation, there are only two categories of needs. According to this theory, in the workplace, along with certain factors that cause job satisfaction, there

is also a separate set of factors that cause job dissatisfaction. The theory is based on human needs. In the late 1950s, F. Herzberg conducted a study. At the request of a psychologist, 200 engineers and accountants at a large firm described situations in which their work was particularly satisfying and when they particularly disliked it. As a result of the experiment, Herzberg came to the conclusion that there are two main categories of factors that assess the degree of satisfaction from the work performed: factors that keep you at work and factors that motivate you to work.

Factors that keep you at work (hygiene factors) are the company's administrative policy, working conditions, wages, and interpersonal relationships with bosses, colleagues, and subordinates.

Factors that motivate people to work (motivators) are achievements, recognition of merits, responsibility, and opportunities for career growth.

Hygiene factors are related to the environment in which the work is performed. According to Herzberg's theory, the absence or lack of hygienic factors leads to a person's dissatisfaction with his work. But, if they are presented in sufficient volume, they do not cause satisfaction in themselves and are not able to motivate a person to the necessary actions.

The absence of motivators, which are related to the nature and essence of the work itself, does not lead to people's dissatisfaction with work, but their presence causes satisfaction and motivates employees to take the necessary actions and increase efficiency.

It should be noted that Herzberg made the paradoxical conclusion that wages are not a motivating factor. On the other hand, it is true that it is a motivator only up to a certain point.

Table 1. Hygienic and Motivating Factors in Herzberg's Theory

Hygienic factors	Motivating factors
Organization and Leadership Policies	Success
Working Conditions	Career Advancement
Wages, social status	Recognition and endorsement of work
Interpersonal relationship with the boss, colleagues and subordinates	A high degree of responsibility
Degree of direct control over Work	Opportunity for creative and professional growth

Thus, non-financial motivation as a management function occupies one of the first places in the managerial activities of managers of successful organizations.

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